

**PRESCHOOL CHILDHOOD IS A PERIOD OF COGNITION AND
DEVELOPMENT OF WORLDVIEW**

Teacher of the Department of Education of Kokand University

Mamamyusupova Iroda Khamidovna

Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Associate Professor.

Abstract: This article examines the problem of cognitive development and the period of initial personality formation, the emergence of emotional anticipation of the consequences of one's actions, self-awareness, the complexity of experiences and awareness, enrichment with new feelings and motives. It has been revealed that the sphere of emotional needs is complex.

Key words: cognitive development, person, formation, behavior, emotional perception, self-awareness, experience, emotion, motive, needs, worldview.

INTRODUCTION

Any person is in a constant process of learning about the world: he thinks, reflects, speaks and understands the speech of other people, feels, shares his feelings. All these abilities develop and improve not on their own, but through active cognitive activity. Preschool childhood is also a period of learning and developing this worldview. The child demonstrates them in role play, which becomes the leading activity. He plays and learns to communicate with peers. This is also a time of creativity. The child learns speech and develops imagination. This is the period of initial personality formation, the emergence of emotional anticipation of the consequences of one's actions, self-awareness, the complication of experiences and awareness, the enrichment of new feelings and motives, a period of complication in the field of emotional development. needs.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

Cognitive milestones are important milestones in a child's development. Throughout human history, babies have often been thought of as simple, passive

creatures. Until the 20th century, children were generally considered miniatures of adults. According to psychologist Jean Piaget, children think differently than adults, and people have begun to view adolescence and young adulthood as a period of unique growth and development. Adults often ignore the extraordinary intellectual abilities of infants and very young children. But modern thinkers and researchers have discovered that children really learn, think and experience the world around them. The problem of cognitive development, conditions that effectively influence the formation of cognitive activity in preschool children for many years and the leader of pedagogical research took one of the places. Cognitive development in preschool age is a qualitative and quantitative development that occurs under the influence of the environment, as well as in thinking processes associated with specially organized educational influences and the child's own experience, the sum of changes. The mental development of preschool children depends on a number of social and biological factors.

from 3 to 4 years

Children have the ability to analyze the world around them in more complex ways. As they observe things, they begin to separate and classify them into different patterns, often called schemas. As children become more active learners, they also ask questions about the world around them. For what? becomes a very common question at this age.

By age three, most children:

- Demonstrate past and present knowledge

Answer questions actively

- Learn by watching and listening to the show

Organize devices by size and shape

- Understand grouping of objects and matching by color.
- Be more focused for 5-15 minutes.
- Encourage asking “why” questions

from 4 to 5 years

As children approach school age, they become better at using words, imitating adults' actions, counting, and performing other activities important to school readiness.

Most four year olds:

Rishma

- Select and highlight multiple colors
- Draw a human figure.

It's equal to five

- Tell me where they live

They often take pictures of names and descriptions. Cognitive development is associated with the non-speech development of M.M. Alekseeva, V.I. Yashin, V. Kojakar and S.A. Kozlova said that pedagogical conditions play an important role in ensuring the sustainable interests of the child, D.B. Godovikova says that the desire to understand the world around us in cognitive activity is both a cognitive need and a cognitive activity motivated by it. A special task of mental education A.Z. Zaporozhets considers a system of basic knowledge and life events to be a condition for mental development. Cognitive psychology covers all emotional processes - from emotions to perception, pattern recognition, attention, learning, memory, to concept formation, covers intervals I. It covers thinking, imagination, remembering, language, emotional and developmental processes, and all types of behavior. Cognitive psychology is a psychological concept focused on the cognitive process and the activities of the mind. Cognitive psychology is a branch of modern psychology that studies cognitive processes. It originates from the work of W. Wolfgang Köhler (1917) on monkeys and Jean Piaget's observations on the development of intelligence in children (1927). Even ancient thinkers tried to figure out where memory and thought are located. It emerged as an independent field in the 1950s and early 1960s, when D. Miller and D. Bruner created the first Center for Cognitive Research at Harvard University in 1960. Well-known representatives of cognitivism are also R. Atkinson, L. Festinger, D. Kelly and

others. The past of the cognitive movement is associated with E. S. Tolman. This researcher recognized the importance of considering cognitive variables and was instrumental in moving away from the stimulus response method. Tolman introduced the idea of cognitive maps, made the case for linking the target category to the actions of animals, and emphasized the need to use intervening variables to identify internal, unobservable states. Cognitive processes are mental processes through which a person understands the world around him, himself and other people. These processes include: sensation, perception, attention, memory, thinking and imagination. The result of cognitive activity is knowledge obtained regardless of the form of knowledge implementation (through thinking or perception). Based on this, A.Z. Zaporozhets special mental education considers his special task to be a system of elementary knowledge and life events as a condition for mental development. When studying the cognitive development of preschool children, one should also take into account the ideas of D. B. Godovikova, who says that cognitive activity is the desire to obtain knowledge about the phenomena of the surrounding world, which is both a cognitive need and a cognitive activity motivated by it. Cognitive activity, in his opinion, has a clear form, on the basis of which its essence can be organized and assessed. According to it, what is the child's interest, what is the intensity of his desire to get acquainted with certain events, can be assessed by 4 indicators:

- Attention to topics and special interest;
- emotional reaction to objects (surprise, confusion, intrigue, that is, various emotions caused by this object);
- Actions aimed at recognizing an object and understanding its functional purpose. The total number of these actions indicates the intensity of the request. But the quality of actions is especially important, first of all their diversity and the replacement of some types with others; the child stops, reflecting on this topic.
- Causes thoughts of persistent pursuit of an object, even if it is not there.

Cognitive development cannot be imagined without speech. As M. M. Alekseeva and V. I. Yashin noted: by mastering speech, the child also acquires knowledge about objects, symbols, actions and relationships, which are reflected in the corresponding words absorbs. At the same time, he not only acquires knowledge, but also learns to think, because to think is to speak quietly or loudly, and to speak is to think. After children master speech, their cognitive activity rises to a new qualitative level. Cognitive curiosity forces children to actively seek knowledge and find ways to satisfy their thirst for knowledge. Children are curious explorers of the world. This feature is characteristic of them from birth. At one time, I.M. Sechenov mentioned “an innate and very valuable property of the neuropsychic organization of a child - an innumerable desire to understand the life around him.” I. P. Pavlov called this property “what is it?” defined as a reflex. Under the influence of this reflex, the child learns the properties of objects and establishes new connections between them. Scientific research activity, characteristic of a child from an early age, develops and strengthens his cognitive attitude towards the world. After children master speech, their cognitive activity rises to a new qualitative level. Cognition of children through speech Generalized, analytical and synthetic ability is formed not only on the basis of direct perception of objects, but also on the basis of ideas.

V. Kojakar and S.A. Kozlova identified pedagogical conditions that ensure fairly stable interests of preschoolers:

creating an enriched scientific-spatial environment to initiate the development of interest; organization of cognitive search for children; participation in the implementation of creative tasks; combine different types of activities; formation of children’s psychological attitude towards future activities; creating a problematic search situation; turn on entertainment; encouraging the manifestation of a child’s positive emotional reaction to events, objects and activities, using sufficient means and methods at each stage of interest formation A child’s self-esteem also begins to develop in kindergarten. When children come to

kindergarten, they try not to notice their peers at first. Later, during various games and compulsory activities, they join the children's group and try to win the respect of their peers, that is, they strive to please other children in everything. The role of moral motivation in the development of behavioral motives of children in kindergarten is extremely large. As children become aware of their behavior, the role of moral motivation, that is, motivation to follow public moral rules, increases. Children begin to learn to act from the point of view of the public good, and not based on their own selfish interests. Older kindergarteners always strive to help younger ones, that is, they act based on social motives. The role of moral motivation in the development of behavioral motives in preschoolers is extremely large. In children of this age, motives for following social and moral rules play an important role. Along with these motives, self-awareness and assessment of their own actions begin to form in children of kindergarten age. For example, through expressive reading or production of such stories as “The Three Bears”, “Uycha”, “Valuable Brothers”, children are brought up to be self-aware and evaluate their own behavior.

CONCLUSION

The problem of cognitive development, conditions that effectively influence the formation of cognitive activity of preschool children, has for many years occupied one of the leading places in psychological and pedagogical research. By studying the features of the cognitive development of preschoolers, we can determine the role of various psychological factors in the cognitive development of a preschooler, what general features of cognitive development develop at this age and what cognitive consequences are caused by the influence of each factor is in a constant process of cognition: he thinks, reflects, speaks and understands the speech of other people, feels, shares their feelings. All these abilities develop and improve not on their own, but through active cognitive activity. Preschool childhood is also a period of learning and developing this worldview. The child demonstrates them in role play, which becomes the leading

activity. He plays and learns to communicate with peers. This is also a time of creativity. The child learns speech and develops imagination. This is the period of initial personality formation, the emergence of emotional anticipation of the consequences of one's actions, self-awareness, the complication of experiences and awareness, the enrichment of new feelings and motives, a period of complication in the field of emotional development. needs.

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